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EFFECT OF HYDROGEN SULFIDE SYNTHESIS ENZYME INHIBITION BY ESTIMATION OF MUCIN IN PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS-INDUCED ULCERS IN MICE

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The present study was undertaken to evaluate the effect of Hydrogen Sulfide synthesis blocker induced enzyme inhibition by estimation of mucin in Psychological Stress-Induced Ulcers in Mice. **Material and methods:** Acute ulcers were induced in Swiss albino mice by using stress. The experimental groups consist of the following 2 groups: sender, responder groups. Sender animals received a foot shock of 10 sec duration at intervals of 50 sec for 3 hour. The electrical current for the shock 1.6 mA to 2.0 mA per hour for 3 day sender animals are changed daily. On day-3, after completing the foot-shock period, the responders were sacrificed, and their stomachs were removed. Drug (O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemihydrochloride) was administered intraperitoneally with low (2mg/kg), medium (5 mg/kg), high (10 mg/kg) dose daily for 3 days respectively, 30 min before the shock period. **Result:** The proper development of ulcer with an average ulcer index of 5 mg/kg was found to be 33.42 which are significant with respect to control group. CBS at a dose of 5 mg/kg significantly increased the ulcer formation, which was corroborated by histopathology studies. **Conclusion:** The present study that observed inhibition of H₂S synthesis blocker exacerbated the psychological stress induced ulcer implicacy an important role of H₂S in regulator of stress.

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INTRODUCTION

Stress is defined as an acute threat to the homeostasis of an organism. Stress evokes adaptive responses that serve to defend the stability of the internal environment [1]. Ulcers are an open sore of the skin or mucus membrane characterized by sloughing of inflamed dead tissue. The peptic ulcers are erosion of lining stomach or the duodenum. The two most common types of peptic ulcer are called “gastric ulcer” and “duodenal ulcer” [2]. Functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGID) are associated with increased anxiety and depression and have a large negative impact on the quality of life. Three of the most common types of FGID are irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), functional abdominal pain, and functional dyspepsia [3].

Hydrogen sulfide along with carbon monoxide and nitric oxide is an important signalling molecule and it is involved in various physiological activities associated with vascular contractility, pro- and anti-inflammatory activities [4]. Endogenous hydrogen sulfide is produced from L-cysteine by cystathionine gamma lyase and cystathionine beta synthase (CSE and CBS), and 3-mercaptopyruvate sulfurtransferase (3-MST) [5].

H₂S is implicated in maintaining GI mucosal defence. Administration of inhibitors of CSE or CBS over the course of a week is reported to result in significant inflammation along the length of the GI tract. The important role play of H₂S in modulated GI inflammation, repair and discuss the potential use of H₂S release drug in treatment of the inflammatory bowel disease and NSAIDs. The H₂S synthesis was found as specify regulated sites of mucosal ulceration and reduce the rates of inactivation of H₂S [6].

O-CHH is used like a nonspecific inhibitor for CBS. This is also effect endogenous H₂S level by inhibiting the activities of CBS and / or CAT [7]. AOAA is soluble in physiological saline solution and the pH was adjusted to 7.4 by using a NaOH. AOAA was tested on membrane potential and spontaneous motility. AOAA did not depolarize on the smooth muscle cells and produced a transient increase in motility [8]. Previous studies done in our laboratory indicate an important role of H₂S in pathophysiology of stress induced ulcers in mice. It was demonstrated that L-Cysteine a H₂S doner produced marked improvement in the prognosis of stress induced ulcers [5]. O-CHH is also called AOAA.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

The drug O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemihydrochloride have been used for study (Sigma Aldrich USA company). A communication box apparatus was used to expose the mice to conditioned emotional stimuli (CES).

Method

All experimental procedures and protocols used in this study were revised and approved by the Institutional animal ethical committee (IAEC) of college of pharmacy IPS Academy, Indore, constituted under committee for the purpose of control and Supervision on Experiment on Animals (CPCSEA).

The experimental groups consists of the following 2 groups: sender group, responder group. Sender animals received a foot shock of 10 sec duration at intervals of 50 sec for 3 hour. The electrical current for the shock is increased step-wise from 1.6 mA to 2.0 mA per hour. Responders were exposed daily to the emotional responses of sender animals, 3h per day for 3 day sender animals are changed daily to naive mice to prevent a reduced emotional response to foot shock based on adaptation or learned helplessness due to repeated exposure. Both sender and responder animals were placed individually in each compartment of the communication box 15 min before beginning the shock period. On day-1, responder animals were returned to their home cages after the 3hr foot shock period.

On day-2, after the completing foot shock period, they were transferred to metal cages and were housed in the cages with 4 animals per cages under food deprivation condition. Food yoked control animals were maintain to the metal cage during foot shock period under the aggregated housing condition (4 animal each) and they were returned to the home cages after the foot-shock period. From beginning of the day-2 experiment, they were maintained in the metal cages under the aggregating housing.

On day-3, just after the completing the foot-shock period, the responders were sacrificed by chloroform, and their stomach were removed. The stomach were visually inspected for lesions. Drug (O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemihydrochloride) were administered intraperitoneally with low (2mg/kg), medium (5 mg/kg), high (10 mg/kg) dose daily for 3 days respectively, 30 min before the shock period.

Method of sacrifice

- Cervical dislocation method.

Method of gastric fluid collection:

- Mice was sacrificed and dissected.
- Pylorus portion was tied through a thread.
- Stomach was isolated and pylorus portion was cut.
- A syringe filled with distilled water was passed through oesophagous and gastric fluid oozed out from pyloric section.

Fig 1 Administration of CHH intra-peritoneally.

Experimental Design

Group I : Control

Group II : O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemihydrochloride (2 mg/kg)

Group III: O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemihydrochloride (5 mg/kg)

Group IV: O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemihydrochloride (10 mg/kg)

Group V: Dizepam

Determination of gastric pH

After the collection of gastric juice from stomach in test tube. Add 1-2 drops phenolphthalein indicator. And titrate with 0.01 N NaOH. Titrate the solution until the colour changes from purple to colourless. Note the volume of NaOH consume from the burette.

$$\text{Acidity} = \frac{\text{Volume of NaOH} \times \text{Normality of NaOH}}{0.1} \times 100 \text{ mEq/lit/100 g}$$

Estimation of mucin

After the collection of gastric juice; the stomach were cut from lesser curvature and everted. The everted stomachs were drenched for 2 hr in 0.1% alcian blue 8 GX dissolved in 0.16 M sucrose buffered with 0.05 M sodium acetate accustomed to a pH with hydrochloric acid. Uncomplexed dye was detached by two consecutive washes of 15 and 45 min with 0.25 M sucrose solution. Dye complexed with mucus was diluted by dipping it in 10 ml aliquots of 0.5 M magnesium chloride for 2 h.

Fig 2 A) Everted stomach for estimation of mucin B) Everted stomach dipped in alcian blue for estimation of mucin.

The resulting blue solutions were shaken vigorously with an equal volume of diethyl ether and the absorbance of the aqueous phase was measured at 605 nm using UV Spectrophotometer. The mucin content of the sample was determined from the standard curve of alcian blue, which has been expressed in microgram/gram of wet gland tissue [9]. The results has been shown in table 2 after the evaluation of ulcer index (Table 1).

Statistical Analysis

All values are expressed as mean \pm SD. The values obtained for the above parameters in case of the test group were compared with control group by using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's test. $p < 0.05$ was considered as significant. Graph pad prism software was used for statistical analysis.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

The Effect of O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemichloride administration on the mean ulcer index of mice is shown in table 1. One way ANOVA revealed a significant influence of O-CHH treatment on the UI of mice [$F(3, 13) = 33.42; P < 0.001$]. Further, analysis revealed that CHH reduced the gastric erosion significantly at 5 mg/kg doses ($P < 0.05$) with maximum increase observed at 10 mg/kg.

The Effect of O- carboxy methyl hydroxylamine hemichloride administration on the gastric pH of mice. One way ANOVA revealed a significant influence of O-CHH treatment on the gastric pH of mice [$F(3, 13) = 38.05$; $P < 0.001$]. Further, analysis revealed that CHH increased the gastric pH significantly all doses ($P < 0.05$), with maximum increase observed at 10 mg/kg.

Table 1. Psychological stress induced ulcers in mice.

S. no.	Treatment	Red coloration (0.5)	Spot (1)	Streaks (1)	Hemorrhage (0.5)	Perforation (5)	Ulcer index
1.	Control						
a.	1 st animal	1	0	0	0	0	0.5
b.	2 nd animal	1	1	0	0	0	1.5
c.	3 rd animal	1	0	0	0	0	0.5
d.	4 th animal	1	0	0	1	0	1.0
2)	Standard						
a.	1 st animal	0	0	0	0	0	0
b.	2 nd animal	0	0	0	0	0	0
c.	3 rd animal	0	0	0	0	0	0
d.	4 th animal	0	0	0	0	0	0
3)	Low dose (1mg/kg)						
a.	1 st animal	1	3	3	2	2	17.5
b.	2 nd animal	1	3	2	1	1	11.5
c.	3 rd animal	0.5	2	2	1	1	9.75
4)	Medium dose (5mg/kg)						
a.	1 st animal	0	4	4	1	0	8.5
b.	2 nd animal	1	1	6	0	0	7.5
c.	3 rd animal	0	2	2	2	1	10
5)	High dose (10 mg/kg)						
a.	1 st animal	0	0	0	0	0	0
b.	2 nd animal	0	0	0	0	0	0
c.	3 rd animal	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Estimation of mucin.

Group	Treatment	No. of animal used	Dose	Mean±SD
I	Control (saline)	4	0.2ml	5.491±1.14
II	Low dose (CBS Antagonist)	4	1 mg/kg	2.370±0.121
III	Medium dose (CBS Antagonist)	3	5 mg/kg	2.754±0.125
V	Standard (Dizepam)	4	0.5 mg/kg	2.100±0.156*

*Significantly different from psychological stress induced ulcer

CONCLUSION

The present study that observed inhibition of H₂S synthesis blocker exacerbated the psychological stress induced ulcer implicacy an important role of H₂S in regulator of stress induced effects on physiology.

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